

INTERFACIAL EVALUATION AND NONDESTRUCTIVE CURE MONITORING OF CARBON FIBER/EPOXYACRYLATE COMPOSITES WITH UV AND THERMAL CURING USING ELECTRO-MICROMECHANICAL TECHNIQUES

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SUMMARY: Interfacial properties and cure monitoring of single-carbon fiber/thermosetting composites with different curing processes were investigated using electro-micromechanical test. During curing process, residual stress was monitored by the electrical resistance measurement, and then they were compared with various curing processes. In thermal curing case, tensile strength and modulus of epoxyacrylate matrix were higher than those of UV curing case, whereas failure strain was lower. Interfacial shear strength (IFSS) increased gradually with elapsing ultraviolet (UV) curing time, and then they were saturated. For thermal curing, IFSS was higher than that of UV curing, and the cure shrinkage appeared significantly by matrix shrinkage and residual stress due to the difference in thermal expansion coefficient (TEC). The change in electrical resistance (ΔR) during thermal curing was larger than that of UV curing. In thermal curing, apparent modulus indicating matrix modulus and interfacial adhesion was highest and reaching time up to same stress was shortest. So far thermal curing shows strong durability on the IFSS after boiling test.

KEYWORDS: interfacial evaluation, ultraviolet (UV) curing, electrical resistivity (ER), residual stress, apparent modulus

INTRODUCTION

Thermosetting resins such as modified epoxy, unsaturated polyester (UP) and vinyl ester can be cured by thermal process involved room temperature, ultraviolet (UV) radiation and

combination of above two methods. UV curing process has attractive advantages compared to thermal curing. Their major advantages are a high-speed process, low energy consumption due to the operation at room temperature, and environmental friendliness by avoiding solvent [1,2]. The electro-micromechanical technique had been studied as an economical and new nondestructive evaluation (NDE) method for cure monitoring, stress or strain sensing, characterization of interfacial properties, and nondestructive behavior because conductive fiber can act as a sensor in itself as well as a reinforcing fiber [3,4]. Residual stress in the fiber-reinforced composites occurs during curing process due to the thermal contraction of the matrix and/or the difference in thermal expansion coefficient (TEC) between fiber and matrix. The effect on residual stress is reflected in the mechanical performance of cured composites [5]. Chung *et al.* [6] measured electrical resistivity to evaluate curing characteristics and micromechanical properties. The relationship between residual stress and the change in electrical resistivity ($\Delta\rho$) during curing was studied in single-carbon fiber/epoxy composites. Interfacial shear strength (IFSS) is an important factor to evaluate the mechanical properties in the fiber reinforced composites. The most common micromechanical techniques to evaluate IFSS include the single-fiber pullout test [7] and the fragmentation test [8,9] etc.

In this work, interfacial properties, damage sensing and cure monitoring of carbon fiber reinforced epoxyacrylate composites were investigated using micromechanical test and electrical resistance measurement. The change in electrical resistance (ΔR) during curing process, under uniform or changeable cyclic stress/strain and durability test was correlated with mechanical properties of matrix based on curing conditions.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials

Two kinds of carbon fibers were used and their average diameters were about 18 μm (Mitsubishi, Chemical Co., Japan) and 8 μm (Taekwang Co., TZ-307, Korea), respectively. E-glass (Dow Corning Co.) and C-glass fibers (Gangnam Co., Korea) were used and their average diameters were about 30 μm and 10 μm . Epoxyacrylate resin (Kunsul Chemical Co., Korea) was used as a matrix, and 1-hydroxy cyclohexyl phenyl ketone (IR-184C, Ciba Co., Switzerland) was used as a photoinitiator.

Methodologies

Specimen Preparation and IFSS Measurement

Carbon fibers with 18 μm in diameter were fixed with regularly separated distance in a steel frame. Microdroplet of epoxyacrylate matrix was formed on each fiber axis using carbon fiber of 8 μm in diameter. Microdroplet specimen was cured via same curing steps. The size of

microdroplet was measured individually using an optical microscope attached with a calibrated eye's lens. The size distribution of microdroplet was in the range of 50 μm to 300 μm and the number of microdroplet was about 40 EA to 50 EA for each case. In microdroplet test, applying load could develop the shear force at the interface. A microdroplet specimen was fixed by the microvise using a specially designed micrometer. The IFSS, τ was calculated from the measured pullout force, F using the following equation,

$$t = \frac{F}{p D_f L} \quad (1)$$

where D_f and L are fiber diameter and fiber embedded length in the matrix resin, respectively. It is assumed that there is a linear relationship between pullout force and embedded length of the fiber.

Fig. 1 Experimental schemes for (a) UV curing process and electrical resistance measurement, (b) during curing, and (c) under cyclic loading

Electrical Resistance (ER) Measurement

Figure 1 shows the scheme of (a) UV curing process and electrical resistance measurement (b) during curing and (c) under cyclic loading. During curing process and under cyclic loading, the electrical resistance was measured using a digital multimeter (HP34401A). For durability test the specimen was soaked in 98°C boiling water for 3 hours and absorbed moisture was evaporated during the electrical resistance measurement. For the electrical resistance measurement under cyclic loading, strain-stress curves were measured by mini-UTM (Hounsfield Test Equipment Ltd., U.K.). Testing speed and load cell were 0.5 mm/minute and 100 N, respectively. Electrical resistance was measured by four-point probe method, and silver paste was used as electrically connecting glue at 4 junctions to maintain electrical contact between the fiber and leading wire. The calculation method of the electrical resistivity, r is as follows:

$$r = \left(\frac{A}{L_{ec}} \right) \times R \quad (2)$$

where R is electrical resistance, A is the cross-sectional area of conductive fiber, and L_{ec} is the electrical contact length between voltage contacts.

Fig. 2 Stress-strain curve for epoxy-acrylate matrix with thermal and UV curing

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Mechanical Properties and Cure Shrinkage

Figure 2 shows stress-strain curve of epoxyacrylate matrix with thermal and UV curing. For thermal curing, tensile strength and modulus of epoxyacrylate matrix was higher than those of UV curing case, whereas elongation was lower. The result indicated that in thermal curing case, the cure degree could be higher compared to UV curing. In UV curing case, tensile strength and modulus increased with UV curing time, whereas elongation decreased. The result means that brittleness of epoxyacrylate matrix increased with increasing UV curing time. It should be due to increasing the degree of cure.

Fig. 3 Cure shrinkage for various fibers/epoxyacrylate composites with (a) thermal and (b) UV curing

Figure 3 shows photographs of cure shrinkage for various fibers/epoxyacrylate composites in (a) thermal and (b) UV curing. The shrinkage phenomenon may depend on cure and

thermal shrinkages. For thermal curing, fiber waviness was observed for all fibers due to high cure and thermal shrinkages, and good interfacial adhesion. For UV curing, fiber waviness was not observed for any fiber. It might be because of the fast curing time without thermal process and low interfacial adhesion. The residual stress could be evaluated indirectly by the observation of fiber waviness in fiber-reinforced composites.

Cure Monitoring

Figure 4 shows the temperature change in (a) air and (b) with epoxyacrylate matrix during curing. For air state without matrix, temperature increased smoothly, and then decreased during cooling process. In case of epoxyacrylate matrix, temperature increased suddenly due to the heat of curing. The results indicated that cure reaction of epoxyacrylate was progressed by UV.

Fig. 4 Temperature change (ΔT) in (a) air and (b) with epoxyacrylate matrix during UV curing

Fig. 5 Cure monitoring for single-carbon fiber/epoxyacrylate composites during (a) thermal and (b) UV curing

The increment of residual stress for single-carbon fiber/epoxyacrylate composites with different curing process can be evaluated by the measurement of ΔR during curing process.

Figure 5 shows ΔR for (a) thermal and (b) UV curing. For both thermal and UV curing cases, the phenomenon of negative temperature coefficient (NTC) [10] appeared for carbon fiber in the given temperature range. NTC means the disproportional of electrical resistance with increasing temperature. Electrical resistance decreased with increasing temperature, and then they increased during cooling process. The change in temperature (ΔT) was corresponded reversibly with electrical resistance. The final electrical resistance was higher than that of the initial state. ΔR during curing may be affected by matrix thermal shrinkage or residual stress by matrix mechanical properties. External stress induced by cure and thermal shrinkage could be transferred to carbon fiber through the matrix. The higher cure and thermal shrinkages, the higher ΔR . For UV curing, electrical resistance decreased suddenly by heat of matrix curing, and then increased gradually with elapsing time. ΔR during UV curing was smaller than that of thermal curing. The result indicates that residual stress in thermal curing is larger than that of UV curing case in Figure 3(a).

Fig. 6 (a) Force-extension curve and (b) IFSS for carbon fiber/epoxyacrylate composites with thermal and UV curing

IFSS and Microfailure Mode

Interfacial properties of carbon fiber-reinforced epoxyacrylate composites were measured by microdroplet test and were compared with different curing conditions. Figure 6(a) shows the force-extension curves with thermal and UV curing. Applied force was transferred from matrix to fiber until the maximum force reached and then pulling-out occurred. After pulling-out, the frictional force appeared differently with fiber surface roughness and interfacial adhesion, etc. The maximum pullout and frictional forces of thermal curing case were higher than those of UV curing. It might be due to high cross-linking density and interfacial adhesion. Figure 6(b) shows the IFSS of carbon fiber/epoxyacrylate composites with curing method and UV curing time. IFSS of carbon fiber/epoxyacrylate composites cured by thermal process was higher than UV curing case. In UV curing the IFSS was improved with increasing UV curing time up to 5 minutes, and then saturated due to the difference in the degree of cure.

Figure 7 shows typical microfailure modes for the carbon fiber reinforced epoxyacrylate

composites with (a) thermal and (b) UV curing. For thermal curing, epoxyacrylate microdroplet exhibited more likely plastic deformation and ductile microfailure mode, whereas in UV curing case microdroplet appeared brittle microfailure mode due to their low the degree of cure. Meniscus angle between fiber and matrix by thermal curing was lower than that of UV curing. It might be because in thermal curing the viscosity of epoxyacrylate matrix cured at high temperature was lower compared to UV curing case. The scale of meniscus angle can determine surface wettability and interfacial adhesion phenomenally.

Fig. 7 Typical microfailure modes for carbon fiber/epoxyacrylate composites with (a) thermal and (b) UV curing

Fig. 8 The change in stress and electrical resistivity under uniform cyclic strain

Fig. 9 The change in strain and electrical resistivity under changeable cyclic stress

Fiber Damage Sensing and Durability

Under the same strain, the stress of single-carbon fiber/epoxyacrylate composites for measuring electrical resistance appeared differently with their mechanical properties of matrix. Figure 8 shows the change in stress for (a) thermal and (b) UV curing under uniform cyclic strain. The stress and strain was corresponded reversibly with electrical resistivity. The stress of thermal curing case was higher than that of UV curing case. Figure 9 shows the change in strain and electrical resistivity for (a) thermal curing and (b) UV curing under changeable cyclic stress. The change in strain and electrical resistivity of thermal curing case were higher than those of UV curing, and the reaching time until the same stress was faster in thermal curing. The tendency could be related to their apparent modulus, which provides the interfacial information; i.e., apparent modulus means the fiber modulus embedded in the matrix in stress-strain curve comparing to the carbon bare fiber modulus in itself [11]. Figure 10(a) shows strain-stress curves with curing conditions. The slope in curve was apparent modulus that increased with improving matrix modulus. Apparent modulus was consistent well with $\Delta\rho$ shown in Figure 10(b).

Fig. 10 (a) Stress-strain curve and (b) $\Delta\rho$ -stress for single-carbon fiber/epoxyacrylate composites

Fig. 11 $\Delta\rho$ for single-carbon fiber/epoxyacrylate composites under durability test

Figure 11 shows $\Delta\rho$ for single-carbon fiber/epoxyacrylate composites under durability test. In the initial state, electrical resistivity increased gradually. It could be because evaporating

moisture from matrix resulted in the recovering matrix modulus. For thermal curing, Δn was smaller compared with UV curing case. The amount of moisture absorption was smaller in thermal curing because of high the degree of cure relating to cross-linking density. As UV curing time increased, the amount of moisture absorption decreased. Δn of thermal curing was the smallest because the speed of the recovering modulus was the slowest compared to UV curing case. The durability for moisture adsorption/desorption seems to be higher in thermal curing.

CONCLUSIONS

Interfacial evaluation, nondestructive damage sensing and cure monitoring of single-carbon fiber/epoxyacrylate composites were performed using microdroplet test and electrical resistance measurement. For thermal curing, tensile strength and modulus of epoxyacrylate matrix were higher than those of UV curing, whereas elongation was lower. As UV curing time increased, epoxyacrylate matrix showed more brittle nature. In thermal curing case, the cure shrinkage appeared significantly due to matrix shrinkage and residual stress by the difference in TEC. IFSS of single-carbon fiber/epoxyacrylate composite cured by thermal process was higher than UV curing. In UV curing case IFSS was improved with increasing UV curing time until 5 minutes and then saturated. It may be due to the difference in the degree of cure. ΔR in thermal curing was higher than that in UV curing, which might indicate higher residual stress and better stress transferring. For thermal curing, stress up to same strain was the highest and reaching time until same stress was fastest. The tendency could be related to their apparent modulus, which can provide the interfacial information. The highest apparent modulus for thermal curing was correlated consistently with IFSS and matrix modulus involving cross-linking density. The durability for moisture was higher in thermal curing due to their higher the degree of cure and interfacial adhesion.

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